

Effect of Project Management Leadership on Project Performance, a Case of Strengthening Child Protection and SRHR Project in Bugesera District, Rwanda

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Abstract:- This study intended to establish the effect of project management leadership on project performance of Strengthening Child Protection and SRHR Project in Bugesera district, Rwanda. The study was built on the following specific objectives; to find out the effect of leadership skills performance of SCP and SRHR Project; to institute the effect of leadership experience performance of SCP and SRHR Project; to determine the effect of leadership control on performance of SCP and SRHR Project; and to establish the effect of leadership style performance of SCP and SRHR Project. In addition, for the study to realize the accomplishment of the above objectives, a combination of questionnaires, interviews, documentary reviews and other reports were used. The target population of the study had been 537 employees and project beneficiaries but the considered a sample size of 84 respondents SCP and SRHR in Rwanda Project in Bugesera district and these comprised of they included 73 project beneficiaries and 11 project's staff. To select this study's respondents, the researcher used universal and random stratified sampling techniques for staff and beneficiaries respectively. The study adopted descriptive and inferential statistics whereby correlational and regression analyses were recognized. Findings revealed that the leadership skills help project leaders to have effective and efficient communication strategies and this was supported by 95.2% of the respondents. Secondly, it was learnt that 97.2% of the respondents strongly agreed that project leaders apply leadership experience to plan project effectively. Thirdly, the research results revealed that 96.4% revealed that with leadership communication, there's effective and efficient utilization of project resources. Lastly, in line with leadership style, 89.3% revealed that leadership style supports projects and provides the guidance. As per the results discovered by the help of the SPSS spearman correlation analysis as indicated in the table above, the value of $r_s=0.775$ and $p=0.001$ which explains that there was a strong, positive monotonic correlation between project management leadership and the performance of SCP and SRHR in Rwanda Project in Bugesera District. From the regression equation, it was revealed that holding term leadership skills, leadership experience, leadership communication and leadership style to a constant zero, performance of SCP and SRHR in Rwanda Project in Bugesera District would be 0.252. Based on these results which each

component of project leadership management would improve performance by a big range, this evidences that all the variables were statistically significant in contributing to performance of SCP and SRHR in Rwanda Project. Hence, the null hypotheses were rejected. Based on the findings, the following are the recommendations: concerning the leadership skills, the project staff and management ought to undergo trainings before they begin operations. In addition, the project leaders and management should always be put in place based on their leadership skills related to the project activities. As regards to leadership communication, respondents cited less awareness on the project and participation in the implementation of project's activities.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background of the Study

The origin of project management leadership can be traced back to the early 20th century. In the US, the first large project that required project leadership was the transcontinental railroad, which began construction in the early 1870s. Project management leadership in Germany, Britain and France has been considered an important factor influencing performance and innovation in the workplace. In Sub-Saharan Africa, most people tend to contemplate that in order to gain experience for effective project management leadership, one needs to gain experience and exposure over a period of time. Thus, a study on effect of project management leadership on project performance, a case of SCP and SRHR Project in Bugesera district, Rwanda.

B. Statement of the Problem

With the increasing presence of both local and international non-governmental organizations (NGOs) in Rwanda, questions are emerging as to how effective they are in providing services which may hinder their projects' performance. The Rwanda Governance Board (RGB) 2018 report revealed untimely completed and abandoned organizational projects in the country. In addition, other weaknesses included fraud and budget absorption of part of organizational projects funding. In addition, Transparency International Rwanda report of 2021 cited low level of beneficiaries' awareness and participation in the organizational projects and this was evidenced by 53.4% of the beneficiaries who reported that they are not much aware of project governance structure. Therefore, the above

motivated the researcher to carry out a study on project management leadership and project performance.

C. General Objective

To establish the effect of project management leadership on project performance, a case of Strengthening Child Protection and SRHR Project in Bugesera district, Rwanda.

D. Specific Objectives

- To find out the effect of leadership skills on performance of Strengthening Child Protection and SRHR Project in Bugesera District;
- To institute the effect of leadership experience on performance of Strengthening Child Protection and SRHR Project in Bugesera District;
- To determine the effect of leadership communication on performance of Strengthening Child Protection and SRHR Project in Bugesera District;
- To establish the effect of leadership style performance of Strengthening Child Protection and SRHR Project in Bugesera District.

E. Research Hypotheses

- **Ho1:** There is no significant effect of leadership skills on the performance of Strengthening Child Protection and SRHR Project;
- **Ho2:** There is no significant effect of leadership experience on the performance Strengthening Child Protection and SRHR Project;
- **Ho3:** There is no significant effect of leadership control on the performance Strengthening Child Protection and SRHR Project;
- **Ho4:** There is no significant effect of leadership style on the performance of Strengthening Child Protection and SRHR Project in Bugesera District;

B. Conceptual Framework

Conceptual Framework 1

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Theoretical Review

- **Trait Theory of Leadership:** Traits theory states that leaders are born and not made. This is to say, leadership is largely innate, rather than being developed through learning. The theory should inspire project leaders at Plan International to spearhead their projects towards success.
- **Behavioral Theory of Leadership:** This theory focuses on leaders' behavior and assume that leaders can be made, rather than born and successful. The theory emphasizes that leader's behavior plays an important role in his/her leadership and as a result, is the best determinant of a successful leadership.
- **Contingency Theory:** The contingency theory emphasizes the importance of both the leader's personality and the situation in which that leader operates. The theory states that a leader's effectiveness is contingent on how well the leader's style matches a specific setting or situation.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design: In this study, the researcher adopted both descriptive and correlational research designs. For clarity, the researcher used descriptive design to provide clear quantitative statistics on effectiveness of project management leadership and project performance whereas the correlational research design was adopted plainly because the study results were quantitatively presented for example by use of regression analysis.

Research Population: In this study, the researcher considered target population of 537 employees and beneficiaries of Strengthening Child Protection and SRHR in Rwanda Project in Bugesera District

Sample Size: Since the above population was too big, the researcher had to reduce it and therefore involved 84 respondents as a sample size of this study. To determine this sample size, the researcher used the Slovin's sample size formula.

Sampling Technique: In order to select the right respondents, stratified sampling technique was used. The researcher used this technique because the target population was categorized in different groups. The researcher therefore reached out to them in different gatherings and dates.

Research Data: The researcher used self-administered questionnaire to collect primary data. The responses were based on a five-point Likert Scales. In addition, the researcher conducted an interview with the project manager.

Data Processing: After collecting data, the researcher continued to data processing. First and foremost, the researcher edited the data. Once editing was done, the researcher proceeded to the coding stage. She then coded the data before feeding the raw data into Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software for analysis.

Data analysis: The researcher applied descriptive statistics in form of percent, frequencies, mean & standard deviation. Also, inferential statistics in form of regression analysis and correlation analysis were used to measure correlation among the study variables.

IV. RESEARCH FINDINGS

This study findings were reached in line with the study's objectives:

- Firstly, 95.2% of the respondents strongly agreed that leadership skills help project leaders to have effective and efficient communication strategies while 71.4% of the respondents strongly agreed that leadership skills enable leaders to solve easily problems in the project operations.
- Secondly, 97.2% of the respondents strongly agreed that project leaders apply leadership experience to plan project effectively while 64.3% of the respondents strongly agreed that project leader's experience is reflected by the quality of work.
- Thirdly, 96.4% of the respondents revealed that with leadership communication, there's effective and efficient utilization of project resources; while 95.2% of the respondents strongly agreed that project staffs' roles and responsibilities are clearly defined.
- Furthermore, 89.3% of the respondents revealed that leadership style supports projects and provides the

guidance; while 71.4% of the respondents strongly agreed that project leaders and subordinates have passion towards the performance of the project.

- Lastly, in line with the regression equation results, the findings indicated that all the p-values were less than 0.05% and this is an indication that all the research sub-variables positively and significantly affect the performance of SCP and SRHR in Rwanda Project in Bugesera District. Hence, all the study's null hypotheses were rejected.

V. CONCLUSION

- The study concluded that there is strong positive and significant effect of project management leadership on project performance of SCP and SRHR Project in Bugesera district, Rwanda. This was revealed by both the descriptive and the inferential statistics.
- Therefore, the study's independent variable, project management leadership has significant effect on the study's dependent variable project performance.

A. Recommendations

- Concerning the leadership skills, the project staff and management ought to undergo project management leadership trainings before they begin operations.
- As regards to leadership communication, the top management should set strategies on how to improve and this should be made a culture by the responsible leaders in the project.
- Lastly, officials who delay the project activities and processes should also be handled individually so as other staff could avoid doing similar mistakes in future.

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